
Implementation of NEP 2020 in Teacher Education: Opportunities, Challenges and Future Perspectives

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ABSTRACT

The New Education Policy (NEP 2020) promises to give a new lease of life to the entire teacher training system in India. The focus of this policy is not just to impart bookish knowledge to teachers but to prepare them with the technology, new curriculum and the demands of the times so that they can face the challenges of the 21st century. This paper examines how this policy is being implemented in teacher education, its major objectives, the changes that are taking place in the curriculum and teaching methods and the opportunities and challenges that lie ahead. This policy is not limited to creating a four-year B.Ed. curriculum but also advocates for changing the classroom environment and making teaching student-centered. Secondary sources such as government documents, research articles, academic reports and books have been used to prepare this paper. The gist is that if we adopt integrated B.Ed programmes, continuous teacher training and proper use of technology, both the teaching capacity of our teachers and the classroom environment will change. But where there are so many great opportunities, one cannot turn away from the same ground realities and challenges. The truth is that many of our teacher training institutions—

especially in rural areas—are still struggling with lack of basic facilities, shortage of good trainers, lack of resources like computers and internet and tight funding. In the end, this is what comes out that instead of keeping NEP 2020 on paper, the government, universities, training institutions and we teachers ourselves will have to work together as a team to put it on the ground. If teachers get the right training, funds and digital resources on time and the entire work is monitored continuously, then only will we be able to achieve our real goal. If we look at it, this policy is an excellent and solid blueprint to truly change the world of education and enhance the dignity of teachers.

1. INTRODUCTION

The real strength of any education system is its teachers, because the mental, moral and social development of children depends on them. The quality of education in a country is determined by the ability and expertise of teachers. That is why teacher training programs are designed in such a way that teachers are prepared who are sincere to their profession and can meet the demands of the changing times. There have been attempts from time to time to improve the teacher training system in India but issues like outdated curriculum, lack of practical experience, incomplete training and distance from technology have always been obstacles.

To address these shortcomings and change the educational structure of the country, the government implemented the 'National Education Policy 2020'. The main objective of this policy is to modernize the entire education system, including teacher training. This policy emphasizes that instead of keeping teachers isolated, they should be connected to different disciplines, their skills should be developed and the proper use of technology should be taught in teaching. The education policy considers teachers as the soul of the entire educational process and it has been made mandatory to equip them with modern methods.

Major changes and targets

A few major changes have been proposed under this policy:

- **Four-year B.Ed:** A four-year integrated B.Ed course will be made a mandatory educational qualification for teaching in schools by the year 2030.

- **Continuous training:** Training of teachers will be arranged from time to time to maintain their skills.
- **Practical and inclusive education:** Emphasis will be placed on such education where instead of memorization, learning is done through experience and every class of child gets equal opportunity.
- **Use of modern media:** Technology will be promoted in the classroom so that children develop the ability to think, understand and solve problems.

Challenges and opportunities for implementation

The truth is that in the present era, it has become very necessary to put this new policy on the ground. This is a great opportunity for us to enable our teachers to compete in any corner of the world. But as good as these things sound, fulfilling them is an equally big challenge. Until our schools and colleges get the necessary budget, the best resources and expert teachers to teach, this dream will remain unfulfilled. If we neglect these basic needs, such a big education policy will remain limited to papers only.

Keeping this in mind, this research paper has tried to understand what are the real goals of NEP 2020 with regard to teacher education, what benefits we can get from it and what obstacles stand in its way. This paper also shows how effective this policy can be in improving the declining quality of teacher training in India and preparing them for the challenges of the 21st century.

2. OBJECTIVES OF NEP 2020 IN TEACHER EDUCATION

The National Education Policy 2020 has given the highest emphasis on teacher education to strengthen the educational infrastructure of India. The policy clearly believes that the role of teachers is the most important in the development of the country and providing a good educational environment to children. That is why several important objectives have been set through this new policy to improve the performance of teachers, their accountability, their status in society and the quality of teaching, so that a modern and inclusive education system can be developed that matches the needs of the 21st century.

A major objective of the policy is to raise the standard of teacher training across the country. The fact is that in many of our teacher training institutions, the standard of teaching is weak, the curriculum is outdated and practical experience is not paid attention to. To address these shortcomings, strict rules are being made under NEP 2020 so that only those institutions that are truly capable of imparting quality

education can operate. Admissions will now be based on merit, the curriculum will be modernized and special attention will be paid to teaching methods to prepare the best teachers.

The new policy suggests that by the year 2030, all teacher training programs should be made part of major universities and multidisciplinary colleges. The advantage of this will be that future teachers will not only learn how to teach but they will also get a broad knowledge of science, arts, history and social studies. By studying in such an environment, teachers will develop the ability to think for themselves, understand, create new things and solve problems. According to the policy, a teacher should not only be an expert in his subject but should also know the social and psychological needs of children.

NEP 2020 promotes a culture of practical learning, asking questions and discussing in the classroom by eliminating the traditional method of rote learning. Now the job of teachers is not just to impart information but to instill a love of learning in children and facilitate their path. This is why now during the training, teachers will be given special training in new teaching methods, classroom management skills and how to take children from different backgrounds together.

Teachers will get opportunities to learn new things and keep themselves updated throughout their career. Under the policy, a 'Continuous Professional Development' (CPD) program has been made mandatory, under which every teacher will have to participate in at least 50 hours of training, workshops or online courses a year. This will enable teachers to learn new technologies and skills to teach with the changing times.

In today's era of computers and the internet, if teachers do not know how to use technology, they cannot teach children properly. That is why this policy clearly states that teachers should be given regular training in taking online classes, operating computers and using different methods of the internet. During the Corona days, we have all seen that when schools were closed, this technology saved education, so now there is no choice but to do without it.

The environment of our schools is such that rich and poor, children from different communities, speaking different dialects and some physically weak children also sit in the same class. The entire emphasis of the policy is on the fact that the teacher's training should be such that he understands the background of each child and does not allow any superiority or inferiority complex with anyone in the class. In the training, teachers will be taught the psychology of children so that they embrace every child and create an atmosphere of mutual respect in the class.

The simple and true point is that the sole purpose of this new education policy is to restore the lost respect of teachers in India and improve their teaching ability. This policy wants to prepare teachers who can answer the new challenges and questions of today, so that the country can create a society where every child has an absolutely equal right and opportunity to read and write.

3. MAJOR RECOMMENDATIONS OF NEP 2020 FOR TEACHER EDUCATION

The National Education Policy 2020 has made some very important suggestions to improve the entire system of teacher training and teaching in India. The main objective of these recommendations is to bring the skills of our teachers, their working methods and the declining quality of teaching at par with the best education systems in the world. The policy has laid great emphasis on the fact that teacher training courses should be such that different subjects are taught together, practical work is more, the full use of computers and the internet is taught and the entire focus is on the needs of children.

The biggest and most important suggestion of this policy is that by the year 2030, the minimum educational qualification for teaching in schools will be a four-year integrated B.Ed. course. This new system will include subject depth, teaching methods and practical experience of schools all together within a single course. Educationists (e.g. Kumar, 2021) believe that this four-year integrated course will greatly strengthen the professional performance of teachers and close the gap between textbooks and classroom reality.

Another major change is the establishment of a national standard for teachers, the 'National Professional Standards for Teachers' (NPST). This will determine what the responsibilities, qualities and ethical obligations of a teacher should be at different stages of their career. According to Sharma and Gupta (2022), this national standard will increase the accountability of teachers towards their work, open up avenues for their own development and make it easier to monitor the quality of teaching in educational institutions.

The policy also strongly advocates for continuous training of teachers, i.e. 'Continuous Professional Development' (CPD). NEP 2020 states that teachers should stay connected with workshops, training programs and online courses from time to time throughout their careers so that they can keep learning new teaching techniques. In this regard, Singh (2021) says that this continuous training of teachers is very important to keep pace with the rapid changes in teaching methods and technology in today's era.

In addition, teaching the use of computers and digital resources during teacher training is also an important part of this policy. According to NEP 2020, it is mandatory for all training institutions to teach teachers the correct use of information and communication technology (ICT), online classrooms and digital tools. Researchers like Patel (2021) believe that in today's computerized era, if a teacher is not adept in technology himself, he will not be able to teach children effectively.

The bottom line is that all these suggestions of the National Education Policy 2020 are a serious attempt to transform teacher training into a new, creative and competency-based system. If these reforms are properly implemented, it will not only improve the quality of education in schools but also make our teachers fully prepared to meet the changing needs of society and the challenges of the 21st century.

4. REFORMS IN CURRICULUM AND TEACHING METHODS UNDER NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020

In India, the National Education Policy 2020 has introduced far-reaching reforms in terms of curriculum and pedagogy to transform the traditional structure of teacher training and to adapt the classroom learning environment to the demands of the modern era. The main thrust of this policy is to shift the teaching process from the traditional approach of simply memorizing information (content-based) to one that is competency-based. According to the documents of the Ministry of Education (2020), the main goal of all teacher training programs should be to produce teachers who discourage the tendency of students to memorize or memorize lines and awaken in them a deep understanding of concepts, the ability to solve problems on their own, a critical perspective and creative thinking.

Educational researchers have pointed out that NEP 2020 emphasizes the importance of hands-on learning and student-centered teaching methods in teacher training, rather than textbook knowledge. Hands-on teaching methods—such as project-based learning, collaborative learning, discussion-based classes and teaching through various activities—not only engage students but also make their learning process meaningful (Kumar and Singh, 2021). Therefore, the policy insists that all teacher training institutions should redesign their curricula so that practical teaching experiences and innovative approaches are given priority along with theoretical content.

Another major reform is related to classroom diversity and inclusive pedagogy. According to Sharma (2022), the new education policy strongly feels the need to train teachers in such a way that they can easily meet the educational and psychological needs of children from different socio-economic, linguistic and cultural backgrounds in the classroom, as well as physically challenged (or special needs)

students. This is why gender sensitivity and practical practice of equity-based teaching methods are now being included in the teacher training curriculum so that every child gets equal opportunities to progress without discrimination.

This education policy also promotes interdisciplinary and integrated teaching methods in teacher training. Educationists argue that when the curriculum is based on the interaction of different disciplines, teachers are able to teach by connecting knowledge from different subjects and see education in a broader perspective instead of limiting it to a single area (Patel and Verma, 2021). The sole purpose of all these efforts is to enable teachers to adapt easily in the changing classrooms of the modern era and their performance to be more effective.

Along with changes in the curriculum and teaching methods, reforming the assessment system of students is also an inevitable part of this educational change. This policy emphasizes testing methods that measure students' understanding, practical application of this knowledge and skills rather than testing their memory. Joshi (2021) says in this regard that during teacher training, future teachers will have to be exposed to a new aspect of the examination system, where instead of rote memorization, they should be given regular training to assess the daily performance of children (formative assessment) and to review their own teaching. For this, it is necessary to revolve the examination system around the overall development of the student and his needs.

The conclusion is that the changes being made in the curriculum and teaching sphere under the New Education Policy 2020 are a serious attempt to take teacher training in India out of the old way and into a new era. The main objective of all these reforms is to change the prevailing methods of teacher training, to give a sense of equality to every class of child in the classroom, to develop the ability to teach by combining different subjects and to make the standard of examination based on skills instead of just measuring memorization, so that our entire education system can be prepared according to the practical needs of the 21st century.

5. ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHER TRAINING AND NEW EDUCATION POLICY

The National Education Policy 2020 has laid great emphasis on the use of technology to modernize the entire teacher training system. Given the rapid pace at which the world is moving towards the digital age, NEP 2020 has made it mandatory for teachers to be trained in the proper use of computers, online resources and latest digital devices. The policy believes that technology cannot be

separated from the teaching methods of teachers in India to reach every child and improve the quality of teaching.

Education experts have also acknowledged that technology greatly enhances the teaching methods and professional performance of teachers. According to Mishra and Kohler (2006), in the present era, it is not enough for a good teacher to know only his subject but he should have a complete knowledge of the subject as well as the interaction of teaching methods and technology i.e. 'TPACK'. Under this ideology, the new policy strongly recommends the inclusion of digital literacy, ICT training, online examination methods and technology-based teaching during teacher training.

A major aspect of the policy is to popularize the use of 'Information and Communication Technology' (ICT) during teacher training. Through this, teachers get the best opportunities for digital curriculum, virtual classrooms and online training. A report by UNESCO (2021) states that the proper use of ICT increases the interest of children in the classroom and the performance of teachers manifold. This is why training institutions are now expected to fully prepare future teachers for online and blended learning environments.

The global pandemic Corona had confirmed the inevitability of technology in the educational world. Dhawan (2020) also believes that when schools were locked down, there was no option but online teaching and this difficult time taught the lesson of how essential it is for teachers to be in tune with modern technology. The truth is that when this sudden campaign happened, many of our teachers had to struggle a lot in taking online classes due to lack of proper training. Keeping this ground reality and experience in mind, the New Education Policy (NEP 2020) has advocated for the inclusion of digital training of teachers on a regular basis, so that they can easily adapt themselves to the pace of time and the template of any online environment.

Along with this, the use of digital platforms like 'DIKSHA', 'SWAYAM' and 'e-Paathshala' launched by the Government of India is also an important part of this policy. According to research by Kumar and Rana (2021), these platforms provide teachers with the best opportunities to learn at their convenience, get good educational resources and improve their careers. The policy encourages teachers and institutions to make the most of these government digital resources.

In today's era, artificial intelligence (AI), virtual learning and data-driven educational tools are also becoming a part of teacher training. Holmes and colleagues (2019) argue that modern technology can be very helpful in teaching according to the individual needs of children and in automated testing

systems. NEP 2020 understands the importance of these emerging technologies and suggests incorporating them into educational plans so that our teachers can manage the smart classrooms of the future.

On the other hand, researchers have also identified obstacles in the way of technology. According to Sharma and Gupta (2022), poor internet access in rural areas, lack of necessary resources, financial constraints and sometimes the tendency of teachers not to adopt technology are major obstacles. This digital gap between urban and rural educational institutions poses a major challenge to the path to equal education for all.

In addition, successful use of technology is not just about learning how to operate a computer but also requires pedagogical understanding. Artmer and Leftwich (2010) believe that the success of technology in the classroom depends on the teacher's own attitude, mindset and confidence. Therefore, teacher training programs should not be limited to teaching computers only but should also instill a positive mindset towards educational technology in teachers.

The bottom line is that with the advent of the 'New Education Policy 2020', technology has become an integral part of teacher training. The policy's focus is on developing teachers who can integrate computers, the internet and new teaching methods. It is certain that this digital transformation will provide great opportunities to improve the quality of education but all this will be successful only when there is complete management in schools, the government is constantly supporting them and every teacher has easy access to these digital tools.

6. OPPORTUNITIES, CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS OF NEP 2020 IN TEACHER EDUCATION

The advent of the New Education Policy (NEP 2020) has given hope of a new lease of life to the entire teacher training system in India. The policy emphasizes not only on bookish knowledge but also on the actual performance of teachers, skills in teaching different subjects, digital literacy and practical classroom experiences. These changes are seen as a great opportunity to prepare our teachers for the new and changing needs of today. The truth is that if we adopt integrated teacher education programs, continuous teacher training and the right use of technology, both the teaching capacity of our teachers and the classroom environment will change (Kumar, 2021).

But where there are so many great opportunities, one cannot turn away from the same ground realities and challenges. The truth is that many of our teacher training institutions are still struggling with

lack of basic facilities, shortage of good trainers, lack of resources like computers and internet and tight funding. Keeping pace with this new era of technology has become a big test, especially for institutions in rural areas. Sharma and Gupta (2022) have rightly raised the point that this huge gap between the grand claims of the policy and the actual readiness of our institutions is the biggest hurdle in the way of implementing NEP 2020.

Another major obstacle is related to the training of our teachers themselves and their acceptance of this new thinking. To make this policy truly successful, teachers and their trainers will have to understand and embrace the new way of teaching, competency-based curriculum and digital methods. If they do not get the right training at the right time and full support from the institutions, then these big educational reforms will remain just on paper and we will fall behind in our goal. Researchers also strongly insist that the insistence on not abandoning old traditional methods and fear of change are also slowing down the entire process (Singh, 2021).

Despite all these difficulties and difficulties, NEP 2020 has shown a solid and bright path for the future of teacher education in India. This policy advocates for new experiments, taking children from all walks of life, a research orientation and student-centered teaching. If we can truly bring these reforms to the ground with integrity, then the quality of education and the dignity of teachers in our country will touch new heights. But this depends entirely on the government, universities, training institutions and we teachers ourselves working together as a team.

7. CONCLUSION

The New Education Policy (NEP 2020) is a serious attempt to give a new and right direction to the entire system of teacher training in our country. Its full emphasis is on not just giving teachers bookish knowledge but preparing them according to the requirements of technology, new curriculum and time so that they can face the challenges of the 21st century. This policy is not limited to creating principles like four-year B.Ed but it advocates changing the classroom environment and making teaching student-centered.

But this dream will come true only when we accept the ground realities. We have to provide complete infrastructure in schools and colleges, remove the shortage of funds and the huge gap between cities and villages, which is the internet and computers, must be erased at all costs. If the government, universities and we teachers ourselves work together as a team, then this policy can go beyond papers and truly change our educational world.

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